

Patient Satisfaction in Outpatient Department at Tertiary Care Hospital: A Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract

Introduction: Patient satisfaction is as important as other clinical health measures and is a primary means of measuring the effectiveness of health care delivery. Patient-centered outcomes have taken central stage as the primary means of measuring the effectiveness of health care delivery.

Material and Methods: A total of 400 cases with various complications attending outpatient departments of medical allied specialities between 18 to 65 years were included. We used two-point Likert's Scale in each component of experiences, accessibility of services and the patient satisfaction towards Outpatient Department services.

Results: The overall experience was satisfactory in 93% of participants towards physical facilities at OPD, services by nurses, pharmacy, and registration department. The service procedures were good in 80.25%, 79.50% and 91% towards working time, service procedures and working schedule respectively. The overall level of satisfaction with the accessibility of services was good in 92% of participants and poor in 8%. There was a significant relationship between patient experience, accessibility and patient satisfaction on services at outpatient department ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: The outpatient department services form a vital element to draw a good image of the hospital services and the patients' opinion are essential in quality improvement.

Keywords: Patient Centered Outcomes, Hospital Services, Outpatient Department.

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Introduction

Patients' satisfaction constitutes a significant indicator of the health care quality, which consists an integral part and recognizable indicator of the quality of health care provided. Patient satisfaction surveys can be tools for learning; they can give proportion to problem areas and a reference point for making important decisions of health care providers [1].

A patient is the ultimate consumer of the hospital and expects comfort, care and cure at healthcare facility. With certain expectation on the facilities, they may become either satisfied or dissatisfied [2]. Measuring the patient satisfaction is examined by variety of health service activities, such as availableness, handiness and expediency of services, technical qualification of the health team, communication abilities and the setting

in which medical and nursing care is delivered [3-5]. Satisfaction may be influenced by socio-economic factors, accessibility to the health care services and experience of patients towards health services [6].

Hospitals act as a bridge between people and health service providers. Hospital is responsible for providing a curative as well as preventive care. Consequently, the hospital has two departments-inpatient and outpatient department [7]. It is important to conduct this kind of survey in developing countries to promote patient-oriented health services. The patient satisfaction studies however received comparatively little attention in public or Government sponsored setting in developing countries in particular [8,9]. The present study was designed to assess the patient satisfaction levels towards available facilities, accessibility at outpatient departments at tertiary care hospital.

Materials and Methods

The present cross-sectional study was conducted in the outpatient departments of various specialities in Mahaveer Institute of Medical Sciences, a tertiary care hospital at Vikarabad, Telangana.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Cases attending outpatient departments of various specialities
2. Pharmacy 1 time.
3. Cases between age group 18-70 years.
4. Cases willing to participate.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Cases below 18 years of age.
2. Cases who need emergency attention.
3. Cases with systemic disorders, mental retardation and other neurological disorders
4. Cases who had not completed the review process and not willing to participate in the study.

After obtaining an approval of the institutional ethics committee. A total 400 cases with various complications attending outpatient departments of medical allied specialities in MIMS were recruited for the study. A structured questionnaire was prepared which contains:

1. Socio-demographic characteristics
2. Patient experiences in the outpatient departments of various specialities
 - a. Registration service,
 - b. Services of pharmacy,
 - c. Facilities in OPD's,
 - d. Services by the clinician,
 - e. Services by nurses.
3. Outpatient Department accessibility to cases
 - a. Waiting period,
 - b. Treatment and service procedure.
 - c. Working schedule,
4. Patient Satisfaction
 - a. Accessibility towards clinician
 - b. Courtesy
 - c. Quality of service and care
5. Patient suggestion and comments to improve outpatient departments of various specialities in MMCH.

The data collection process was done by personal interviews. The patient experience and accessibility to outpatient departments of various specialities in MIMC were classified into "Good and poor, high and low" respectively. We used two-point Likert's Scale in each component of experiences, accessibility of services and the patients satisfaction towards Outpatient Department services. As a result, the value of best criteria in the current study was 0.5 (50%). According to the study by Mandokhail AK *et al.* 2007, we evaluated the patient satisfaction and method of scoring. The scores to set the borderline between poor/low and good/high were obtained from multiplying the total scores of a component by the value of best criteria.

The collected data was analyzed by using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics was used to obtain frequencies, mean, standard

deviation. chi-squared test and fisher's exact test was used to compare the study variables.

Results

Table 1: Socio-demographic features of study participants.

Socio-demographic features	Total participants (n=400)	
	Number	Percentage
Age group (In years)		
18-30	174	43.5%
31-40	58	14.5%
41-50	66	16.5%
51-60	60	15%
>60	42	10.5%
Sex		
Male	186	46.5%
Female	214	53.5%
Marital status		
Single	85	21.25%
Married	276	69%
Divorced/Widowed	39	9.75%
Educational status		
Illiterate	35	8.75%
Primary	18	4.5%
Upper primary	22	5.5%
High school	84	21%
Intermediate	114	28.5%
Under graduate	75	18.75%
Post graduate	52	13%
Occupation		
Studying	22	5.5%
Self-employed	46	11.5%
Employee of public sector	32	8%
Employee of Private sector	112	28%
Farmer	33	8.25%
Daily wage workers	102	25.5%
NGO	17	4.25%
Un employed	36	9%

Figure 1: Levels of patients experience towards OPD facilities.

Figure 2: patient feedback on Accessibility of services at various levels of consultation process.

Table 2: Relationship between patient experience, accessibility and patient satisfaction on services at outpatient department.

Parameters	Patient's satisfaction		Chi-square value	Significance
	High	Low		
Registration service				
Satisfied	342	33	1.245	0.722
Not satisfied	15	10		
Services of pharmacy				
Satisfied	214	68	2.864	0.006*
Not satisfied	108	14		
Facilities in OPD's				

Satisfied	351	15	1.022	0.048*
Not satisfied	08	26		
Services by nurses				
Satisfied	264	56	1.986	0.002*
Not satisfied	25	55		
Waiting time				
Satisfied	220	101	2.128	0.745
Not satisfied	64	15		
Working schedule				
Satisfied	298	20	1.064	0.669
Not satisfied	31	51		
Service procedure				
Satisfied	311	53	1.012	0.523
Not satisfied	22	14		
Not satisfied	14	30		

Discussion

Majority participants (87.75%) showed good experiences with registration services, around 69.5% of the participants reported good experiences with pharmacy service. 91.5% were satisfied with facilities at OPD. It was noted that 86% of the participants showed good experience regarding services by nurses (Figure 1). The overall experience was satisfactory in 93% of participants towards physical facilities at OPD lounge, services by nurses, pharmacy, and registration department. However, it was noticed that there was some problem regarding nurses' attention, and registration services. A study by Mohd *et al.*, on Indian armed forces personnels including their dependents attending a tertiary care hospital reported varied levels of satisfaction levels among attributes of the dispensary. While officers and other ranks satisfactory levels were ranges high to moderate, but junior commissioned officers were not satisfied with the dispensary in terms of waiting are, counter, waiting time for collection of medicines [10]. Similarly, in current study few participants were n satisfied with the availability of drugs and explanation for dosages of prescribed drugs and other necessary information. A study by Joshi *et*

al., found that 74% of patients reported that nurse listen to their issues, 68% were agreed for nurses are helpful to them and 74% were agreed for nurses show good communication skills. In the matter of pharmacy service, 78% patients were agreed that the pharmacist explained the details of prescribed drugs and usage and 74% agreed that pharmacist showed good communication skills. The 72% and 84% of patients were reported that the registration staff was cooperative and showed good communication skill [11]. A study by Joshi K *et al.*, reported that the overall availability of services was good i.e., for seating arrangements (97%), for cleanliness in OPD (95%), for OPD timing (93%), and for services provided by the paramedical staff (83%) and for availability of sufficient doctors (85%) [12]. Study by Jawahari *et al.*, reported that, around 50% of the participants were satisfied for cleanliness of hospital [13]. A study by Prasanna *et al.*, reported that the patients were highly satisfied with the services, seating arrangements and cleanliness in the OPD and OPD timings [14].

The service procedures were good in 80.25%, 79.50% and 91% towards working time, service procedures and working schedule

respectively. The overall level of satisfaction with the accessibility of services was good in 92% of participants and poor in 8%. A study by Mohd *et al.*, reported high satisfactory rate for accessibility of OPD location in 81-86% of participants. However, low satisfaction rate was observed in related to parking areas (66%) and signage system (67%) and moderate satisfaction was observed towards cafeteria facility availability (60.65%) [10]. A study by Joshi *et al.*, reported that 66% of patients had good accessibility towards OPD facility, 53% had good accessibility in terms of waiting time, 78% had good accessibility to service process and 82% had good accessibility to working hours [11].

There was a significant relationship between patient experience, accessibility and patient satisfaction on services at outpatient department was found in related to services by pharmacy, services by nurses and facilities at OPD's ($p < 0.05$). A study by Mohd *et al.*, reported a significant difference in mean satisfaction levels among study participants [10]. The present study was limited to focus on the patients attending the OPD's of medical allied specialties. Further analysis is required to focus on the patient satisfaction levels at outpatient and inpatient at all available specialties of health care.

Conclusion

In conclusion, majority of the participants were highly satisfied with the services offered. Patients were satisfied with logistic arrangement, nursing care, and pharmacy services. Nurses' services, and pharmacy's services were found to have significant relationships with patient satisfaction level. It is beneficial to understand that there is an opportunity for the improvement of the outpatient department service. Hence, it can be concluded that the outpatient department services form a vital element to draw a good image of the hospital services and the

patients' opinion are essential in quality improvement.

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